

Artificial Intelligence in the field of Civil Engineering- A Review

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ABSTRACT:

A branch of computer science called Artificial intelligence (AI) deals with the study, creation, and use of intelligent machines. A very large amount of processing power is required to solve difficult problems, but AI-based technologies provide an easier alternative. This includes the description of recently developed ideas and methods for the development and implementation of AI in civil engineering and also gives an overview of the field's advancement. With the tremendous development and advancement in big data, deep learning, and machine learning technologies, it has been used effectively and successfully in various sectors of civil engineering. The important areas of artificial intelligence research in civil engineering include structural management and maintenance, as well as design optimization. Data collection, sustainability assessment, and productivity are just a few advantages and prospects that the use of AI in civil engineering offers to civil engineers. With the use of digital technology, the construction trend has now been transformed into one that emphasizes sustainability. Using of computers in civil engineering is primarily focused on numerical, algorithmic calculations, which is inappropriate for solving the empirical and poorly structured problems that arise in actual practice and are instead handled by expert systems and artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Civil Engineering, Artificial Neural Networks, Big Data, Deep Learning, Genetic Algorithms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence in civil engineering can be defined as a subfield of computer science that deals with the study, development, and use of intelligent computers which plays a crucial role in the digitalization and intelligence of civil engineering and also enables significant improvements in automation, performance, and reliability as well as forging a direct link between the physical and digital construction. The main objective of this field is to investigate different ways to mimic and carry out parts of the brain's cognitive functions so that

Individuals can create technological advancements and establish pertinent hypotheses. The summary of the basic theories and techniques of artificial intelligence is concise symbolism, behaviourism, and connectionism. Since it first appeared in the 1950s, from then there have been various expectations and dreams for artificial intelligence. Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a technology is accepted widely that provides an alternate approach to solving different challenges and various ill-defined issues. Artificial Intelligence has also been utilized for complex system modelling, identification, optimization, forecasting, and control. The categorization of the development of AI includes five different phases

namely: before 1956, the incubation phase, the formation phase, the dark phase, the knowledge application phase, and lastly the integrated development phase (1986-present). As a result of major advancements in data collection and processing hardware, a unique machine learning technique has been recently introduced by artificial intelligence (AI) called Deep Learning (DL). We know that construction is a significant economic sector that has the potential to influence national development and long-term progress, and additionally, governments all over the world are working harder to incorporate artificial intelligence (AI) in order to acquire a competitive edge. Big data is used to teach AI complex algorithms, which are then used for the benefit of the building or construction industry. Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies and systems once trained are capable of making rapid predictions and generalizations in the field of digital building or digital construction and also can handle various difficult and non-linear functional issues. The major courses in civil engineering include several techniques namely: such as civil engineering materials or building/construction materials, different mechanical accessories and equipment, various surveying techniques, different design techniques, varieties of civil construction and maintenance techniques, etc.

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) has great and numerous potential in research on civil engineering. Artificial intelligence i.e. AI is used to enable structured technologies, analysis of data, health protection, planning, managing risk, and making a decision. The use of artificial intelligence (AI) is very helpful on the site for increasing productivity, standard, and protection in the building sector. We are very much aware that neural networks have the capacity to store, memorize, process and evaluate massive amounts of data. The building of roads, repair of pavements, and structural hazard assessment. Reduction of

risk, high-performance computing power calculation, optimization, estimate, categorization, and growth all require the use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

[1] Pengzhen Lu, Shengyong and yujun Zheng

In this study, the intelligent technologies in civil engineering are summarized and introduced together with the latest research findings and applications too. Examination of the use of artificial intelligence technologies in civil engineering is done from every angle possible. The potential applications of artificial intelligence technology in the field of civil engineering were depicted on the basis of the findings of the research carried out. The study concluded that AI has a bright future in the field of civil engineering and can improve both individual and collective productivity.

[2] Yougin Huang, Jiayong and Jiyang Fu

A review of how artificial intelligence has evolved and been used in civil engineering over the years is done in the paper. AI algorithms and civil neural networks have been employed in the field of civil engineering and are frequently used for geotechnical, bridge engineering, health monitoring, structural optimization, and structural status evaluation for many years. Big Data technologies and Deep Learning have been successfully used in a variety of civil engineering applications recently. In particular, Big Data has more advanced quickly in the field of structural maintenance and because of the quick development of Deep Learning based computer vision, the ability to monitor the health of the structures using computer vision has significantly improved. The study's conclusion states that the integration of big data and deep learning will be a new research area for artificial intelligence (AI) in civil engineering.

[3] Bilal Manzoor, et.al

This includes a detailed exploration of the annual publication trend of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in civil engineering towards sustainable development as well as the contributions from top journals in this area,

geospatial distribution, and comparisons between developed and developing nations. The study concluded that automation in construction had a significant impact on artificial intelligence-related publications works and aids in a basic understanding of civil engineering, listing the potential value of artificial intelligence in supporting and enhancing construction work. Discussion of the impact of AI and sustainable assessment, providing sample proof of the

Advantages of AI techniques is also discussed in this.

[4] Yuting Zhang

In this, safety management is adopted as its primary focus and thorough examination of the entire emergency management process which includes the prevention, planning, response, and recovery of civil engineering construction safety incidents. In this, the theory of construction safety incident management is also improved and also encourages the development of emergency response capacity on a practical level. In this, the main focus is on applying artificial intelligence machine vision technology to monitor worker activity during construction in order to ensure worker safety and is done in order to research the application of civil engineering construction safety management. For reflecting the actual distances and trajectories between targets, the establishment of a quantitative relationship between the coordinates and distances of image pixels and the actual coordinates and distances are further investigated.

[5] L.Sgambi

In this, the study and design of complicated structures like long suspension bridges are discussed and state the use of soft computing is provided as a way to increase the accuracy of the study. For addressing the problem's inherent uncertainties and to gain a more thorough understanding of structural behavior, neural networks, evolutionary algorithms, and fuzzy analysis are used.

[6] S. Fenves

A methodology known as a Knowledge-Based Expert System (KEBS), which provides an intellectual framework for addressing heuristic problems in civil engineering which cannot be successfully approached with traditional programming techniques and is based on well-structured, algorithmic formulations are included in this paper along with other various artificial intelligence methodologies and concepts. The needs of KEBS are broken down into four distinct categories namely reasoning with geographical relations and features, interaction with algorithmic components, and interface with databases. Experimentation with the current generation of KBES has shown us to revise traditional engineering knowledge. The conclusion is that KBES will contribute greatly to the expansion of computer-aided engineering from purely computational to true reasoning.

[7] Yoram Reich

In this, the practical uses of Machine Learning in developing a building that calls for proficiency in handling a variety of difficulties are covered. Studying the earlier applications and attempting to characterize different engineering domains helps with improving the understanding of the nature of various learning issues. The majority of studies using machine learning in civil engineering have used supervised concept learning techniques and very similar circumstances have been noted in regard to real-world machine learning applications in general.

[8] Ming Xie, et.al

The domestic AI industry is still in its infancy and there are still some technical flaws in the technology's real use for the sake of teaching civil engineering, these flaws can be overlooked. By the application of intelligent artificial intelligence technology, teachers can help students more effectively to complete their major courses in civil engineering and also develop a fresh group of professional talents for society as soon as feasible.

[9] Dr. Sabih Ahmad, et.al

In many civil engineering fields including prediction, decision-making, risk analysis, resource optimization, classification, and selection among others, Artificial Neural Networks have been effectively implemented and are outperforming other traditional approaches. Civil engineering has varieties of problems that are exceedingly complicated and little understood and many models are not able to explain such complex behavior. It concludes that artificial neural networks are a powerful and useful tool for solving many problems in the field of civil engineering which is also expected to be used in the future since they are based simply on input and output data and have a significant number of possible outcomes.

[10] Shrikanth Kate, et.al

In this, the application of artificial intelligence is covered and discusses various applications of clever optimization techniques to field research and structural engineering. Artificial intelligence can develop and alter over time when computer programs are used extensively. It concludes that the scope of future work is to review or conduct research on applications in a particular field, such as hydrological engineering, construction management, structural engineering, transportation, etc.

[11] Tu T. Nguyen

In this, for forecasting the 28-day compressive strength of fiber-reinforced, high-strength self-compacting concrete using experimental mixtures, ANN and ANFIS models were constructed. This includes different varieties of ANN models created using various training algorithms and the number of neurons in the hidden layer to obtain the best model. The 28-day compressive strength of FRHSSCC was more sensitive to changes in the water-to-cement ratio parameter and less sensitive to changes in the amount of fiber, according to the results of the sensitivity analysis using the ANN model (VOF). Both the ANN and ANFIS models were able to predict the compressive strength accurately.

[12] Zeljka Beljkas

As per the study, it was shown that artificial neural network models with a three-layer neural architecture have the maximum accuracy for predicting the amount of concrete and reinforcement needed to construct integrated road bridges. In this, MAPE i.e. Mean Absolute Percentage Error is used to represent the accuracy measure in both models. It states that the accuracy of a forecasting model can be increased by increasing the number of data in a database. The study comes to the conclusion that the forecasting model could possibly be used more widely if the database were expanded with specific structural features like types of cross-sections, the height of the cross-section, number of spans, number of piers, and structural system. Additionally, the contractor can estimate the amount of material with the aid of a forecast model without having to create the preliminary design and only using drawings as a basis, which is significant in competitive bidding.

3. DIFFERENT TECHNIQUES AND METHODS**3.1 Genetic Algorithms**

It is one of the well-known evolutionary algorithms which imitate the survival of the fittest and the Darwinian theory of evolution in optimization. This has many applications in the field of civil engineering but there are still many areas that need more research and development. Through the development of genetic algorithms, various new mathematical tools are created which is one of the most recent application successes. Its use in the field of civil engineering application is increasingly widespread with the efficient advancement of computer technology. By using genetic algorithms, construction planners can create and assess optimal or nearly optimal construction schedule plans that can save project time and expense using a genetic algorithm-based optimization model for linear construction projects.

3.2 Artificial Immune System

For solving complicated engineering optimization issues in the real world, the artificial immune system activates a living organism's adaptive immune system. Artificial Immune System is a method that solves the drawbacks of the conventional and artificial neural network-based approaches and is used for the analysis of civil engineering systems by combining the evolutionary algorithm with the least square method that determines feasible structures and the relevant constants for the structure. Various immune algorithms have been put out by realization forms but still, the investigation of how to use immune system traits is in its early stages. In the context of civil engineering applications, the immune system still requires development.

3.3 Expert System

It is the first and most successful in the field of artificial intelligence research which is built on the knowledge which is already held by human experts and is established on the established knowledge systems. This technology is used in various areas of civil engineering such as roads, bridges, construction engineering, geotechnical engineering, material engineering, petroleum chemical industries, and other areas extensively.

In the field of structural selection, this system offers a fresh chance for organizing and systematizing knowledge and expertise. Its use in civil engineering is increasing daily with the increase in the use of artificial intelligence techniques, and in the 21st century, these systems will serve as construction management tools and human assistants in the field.

3.4 Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)

This can be described as a system of closely coupled adaptable simple processing units i.e. artificial neurons or nodes that have the capacity to carry out massively parallel computations for knowledge representation and data processing. This is a kind of simplified technical reconstruction of a biological neural network whose primary goal is to create a workable artificial neural network model in accordance with the theory of

biological neural networks and activate some technically implemented intelligent activities of the human brain to address practical issues. This is frequently used in structural optimization, health monitoring, structural control, characterization and modelling of structural materials, construction engineering, highway engineering, etc. This technology's network consists of input, hidden, and output layers which are excellent for jobs involving inadequate data sets, hazy or missing information, and for extremely difficult issues where human judgments are frequently made intuitively.

3.5 Big Data

The quick advancement of big data technology has generated a lot of discussion in the field of science, technology, industry, and even governments worldwide. Engineering, it requires the adaption of data from numerous new sources, including sensors, wireless devices, GPS, and machine-to-machine streaming communication. The continuous, unstructured, and freedom from the strict structure of rows and columns that characterizes data makes it challenging for traditional approaches to handling. So, the applications of big data are urgently needed. The fundamental feature of big data applications is autonomous data with dispersed and decentralized controls since each data source is capable of generating and gathering information without needing or depending on any centralized control.

3.6 Deep Learning

This is a type of machine learning method that uses numerous layers, starting with the raw input to gradually extract higher-level features. The primary use of deep learning in civil engineering is for monitoring structural health using vision. The traditional shallow neural networks are unable to extract high-level features and even require additional post-processing to explain the extracted high dimensional characteristics, whereas deep learning techniques can employ more training data and more complex network architecture to overcome the challenges. With deep learning-based detection

algorithms, pavement fracture and damage identification issues can be successfully addressed. Deep Learning helps in the detection of the performance of the passing train and the structural condition of the track bed by monitoring the vibration of the track bed structure and the identification of analogous signals in railway engineering.

Fig 3.1- Framework.

4. APPLICATION OF AI IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

4.1 Construction Engineering and Management

The behaviour of cement-based materials subjected to single, double, or multiple injuries can be modelled using complicated structures with well-defined input and output data sets using a computational method based on artificial intelligence (AI) called Neuro-Fuzzy Inference Systems. Additionally, it can be utilized to create construction management plans that reduce project costs and length. In cases of the planning stage, the automated machines may examine a potential construction site for

gathering sufficient data to create 3D models, blueprints, and project plans. Before this, it used to take weeks to finish but now with AI, it now just takes a day.

4.2 Structural Engineering

Artificial Intelligence is used to create computational components that analyze human mental processes and replicate them. Sub-structuring techniques, harm recognition approaches, and static and dynamic substructure methods to quantify the harmed elements based on a full and partial estimation are used for a larger scale of artificial intelligence in the field of civil engineering.

4.3 Transportation Engineering

Focusing on the failure traits of highway slopes, an empirical model can be used for evaluating the possible failure of highway slopes. For addressing complex transport networks, a technique named Agent Based modelling (ABM) is more effective than conventional modelling techniques. For handling the issues pertaining to transportation technologies, a Knowledge-Based System (KBS) is employed.

4.4 Structural Damage Detection

A neural network named Faster Region-Based Convolutional Neural Network (Faster R-CNN) is a structural visual inspection technique that simultaneously and in real-time identifies different types of surface damage: bolt corrosion, delamination, steel corrosion, concrete cracking, etc.

4.5 Quantity Surveying

Artificial Neural Networks are perfectly suited for building decision aids with analogy-based problem-solving abilities for surveying difficulties. The model design, training, and testing are defined by the adjustments to generalization made using the Genetic Algorithms technique.

4.6 Geotechnical Engineering

By using a general model of neural network regression, the capability for non-linear liquefaction can be evaluated and this model can be used by geotechnical.

Fig 4.1-Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Construction Industry.

5.5 CONCLUSION

This paper consists of different literature reviews on the application of Artificial Intelligence in the field of Civil Engineering and discusses different techniques and methods of Artificial Intelligence in Civil Engineering along with various applications. There is still more to research and develop the study of

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